

of fused sodium acetate with subsequent cyclisation were made according to Pavlenko.⁴ Thiosemicarbazides are described in Table I and the title compounds are described in Table II.

TABLE I
Thiosemicarbazones.

R'.	M.P.	Formula.	% Sulphur.		M.P.	Formula.	% Sulphur.	
			Found.	Reqd.			Found.	Reqd.
		A. R = <i>o</i> -tolyl.				B. R = <i>p</i> -anisyl.		
Ph	155°	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ N ₃ S	11.6	11.9	106°	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ ON ₃ S	11.2	11.2
<i>o</i> -HO.C ₆ H ₄	189°	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ ON ₃ S	11.0	11.2	210°	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₃ S	10.4	10.6
<i>p</i> - "	222°	"	11.1	11.2	186°	"	10.4	10.6
<i>o</i> -CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	185°	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ N ₃ S	11.2	11.3	140°	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ ON ₃ S	10.5	10.7
<i>p</i> - "	150°	"	11.1	11.3	"	"	"	"
<i>p</i> -CH ₃ O.C ₆ H ₄	200°	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ ON ₃ S	10.7	10.7	160°	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₃ S	10.0	10.2
-CH=CH.Ph	183°	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₃ S	10.0	10.8	155°	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ ON ₃ S	10.1	10.3
<i>m</i> -NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	191°	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₃ S	10.0	10.2	189°	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ O ₃ N ₃ S	9.6	9.8
2,4-Cl ₂ .C ₆ H ₃	225°	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ N ₃ Cl ₂ S	9.4	9.5	202°	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ ON ₃ Cl ₂ S	8.9	9.0
3,4-(CH ₃) ₂ O ₂ C ₆ H ₃	188°	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₃ S	10.0	10.2	195°	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ O ₃ N ₃ S	9.6	9.7
3,4-(OMe)(OH).C ₆ H ₃	210°	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₃ S	10.0	10.2	210°	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ O ₃ N ₃ S	9.5	9.7
α -C ₁₀ H ₇	145°	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₃ S	9.8	10.0	203°	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ ON ₃ S	9.4	9.5

TABLE II
4-Oxo-3-aryl-5-alkyl/aryl-thiazolin-2-yl-hydrazones.

R''.	M.P.	Formula.	% Sulphur.		M.P.	Formula.	% Sulphur.	
			Found.	Reqd.			Found.	Reqd.
		A. R = H; R' = <i>o</i> -tolyl.				B. R = H; R' = <i>p</i> -anisyl.		
Ph	146°	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ ON ₃ S	10.3	10.4	212°	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₃ S	9.7	9.8
<i>o</i> -HO.C ₆ H ₄	160°	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₃ S	9.7	9.8	266°	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ O ₃ N ₃ S	9.2	9.4
<i>p</i> - "	231°	"	8.6	9.8	262°	"	9.2	9.4
<i>o</i> -CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	160°	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ ON ₃ S	9.7	9.9	286°	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₃ S	9.2	9.4
<i>p</i> - "	117°	"	9.8	9.9	"	"	"	"
<i>p</i> -CH ₃ O.C ₆ H ₄	183°	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₃ S	9.3	9.4	205°	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ O ₃ N ₃ S	8.9	9.0
<i>m</i> -NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	192°	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₃ S	8.9	9.0	210°	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ O ₄ N ₃ S	8.5	8.7
-CH=CH.Ph	140°	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ ON ₃ S	9.4	9.6	244°	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₃ S	8.9	9.1
2,4-Cl ₂ .C ₆ H ₃	165°	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ ON ₃ Cl ₂ S	8.4	8.5	250°	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₃ Cl ₂ S	8.0	8.1
3,4-(CH ₃) ₂ O ₂ C ₆ H ₃	201°	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ O ₃ N ₃ S	9.0	9.0	229°	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ O ₄ N ₃ S	8.7	8.7
3,4-(OMe)(OH).C ₆ H ₃	152°	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ O ₃ N ₃ S	8.9	9.0	236°	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ O ₄ N ₃ S	8.5	8.6
α -C ₁₀ H ₇	162°	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ ON ₃ S	8.8	8.9	241°	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₃ S	8.5	8.5

4. *Farm. Zhur.*, Kiev, 1950, No. 4, 3.

TABLE II (contd.)

R''.	M. P.	Formula.	% Sulphur.		M.P.	Formula.	% Sulphur.	
			Found.	Reqd.			Found.	Reqd.
		C. R = Me; R' = o-tolyl.				D. R = Me; R' = p-anisyl.		
Ph	..	..	..	..	183°	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₃ S	9.4	9.4
o-HO.C ₆ H ₄	219°	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₃ S	9.4	9.4	206°	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₃ S	9.0	9.0
p- "	192°	"	9.3	9.4	222°	"	8.8	9.0
o-CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	106°	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ ON ₃ S	9.3	9.5	191°	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₃ S	9.0	9.1
p- "	173°	"	9.3	9.5	..	..	..	..
p-CH ₃ O.C ₆ H ₄	165°	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₃ S	9.0	9.0	204°	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₃ S	8.6	8.7
m-NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	190°	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₄ S	8.5	8.7	177°	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ O ₄ N ₄ S	8.1	8.3
-CH=CH.Ph	..	..	..	..	314°	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₃ S	8.7	8.8
2,4-Cl ₂ .C ₆ H ₃	172°	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ ON ₃ Cl ₂ S	8.0	8.2	203°	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₃ Cl ₂ S	7.6	7.8
3,4-(CH ₃) ₂ O ₂ .C ₆ H ₃	172°	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₃ S	8.0	8.7	175°	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ O ₄ N ₃ S	8.4	8.4
3,4-(OMe)(OH)C ₆ H ₃	..	..	..	..	115°	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ O ₄ N ₃ S	8.3	8.3
α-C ₁₀ H ₇	121°	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ ON ₃ S	8.4	8.6	180°	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₃ S	8.0	8.2
		E. R = Ph; R' = o-tolyl.				F. R. = Ph; R' = p-anisyl.		
Ph	115°	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ ON ₃ S	8.1	8.3	190°	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₃ S	7.9	8.0
o-HO.C ₆ H ₄	220°	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₃ S	7.9	8.0	227°	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₃ S	7.6	7.7
p- "	..	..	..	..	186°	"	7.5	7.7
o-CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	..	..	..	..	220°	C ₂₄ H ₂₁ O ₂ N ₃ S	7.6	7.7
p- "	120°	C ₂₄ H ₂₁ ON ₃ S	8.0	8.0	..	..	..	..
p-CH ₃ O.C ₆ H ₄	166°	C ₂₄ H ₂₁ O ₂ N ₃ S	7.7	7.7	135°	C ₂₄ H ₂₁ O ₂ N ₃ S	7.2	7.4
m-NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	187°	C ₂₃ H ₁₈ O ₂ N ₄ S	7.2	7.4	210°	C ₂₃ H ₁₈ O ₄ N ₄ S	7.0	7.2
-CH = CH.Ph	..	..	..	..	..	..	..	..
2,4-Cl ₂ .C ₆ H ₃	212°	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ ON ₃ Cl ₂ S	7.0	7.0	197°	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₃ Cl ₂ S	6.6	6.8
3,4-(CH ₃) ₂ O ₂ .C ₆ H ₃	117°	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₃ S	7.6	7.5	212°	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ O ₄ N ₃ S	7.0	7.3
3,4-(OMe)(O.H)C ₆ H ₃	122°	C ₂₄ H ₂₁ O ₂ N ₃ S	7.2	7.4	310°	C ₂₄ H ₂₁ O ₄ N ₃ S	7.0	7.2
α-C ₁₀ H ₇	201°	C ₂₇ H ₂₁ ON ₃ S	7.2	7.4	194°	C ₂₇ H ₂₁ O ₂ N ₃ S	7.0	7.1

Hydrolysis of Compound (I: R'=R=Ph).—To the above compound (1 g.), dissolved in acetic acid (5 ml), HCl (ca. 15 ml.) was added and the mixture refluxed on a sand bath for about 2 hr. when a solid separated. The mixture was cooled, filtered, and the product obtained was washed with cold water. It was crystallised from ethanol in colorless needles, m.p. 148°. A mixed melting point with the authentic specimen of (IV: R=Ph; R'=H), prepared according to Wheeler and Barnes⁵, remained undepressed.

Similarly hydrolysis of (I: R'=R=Ph and CH₂ substituted by CHMe) furnished a product melting at 82°, undepressed by mixed m.p. with an authentic specimen of (IV: R=Ph; R'=Me), prepared according to Bhargava *et al.*⁶.